

Abstract Book

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480 THE CLOCK DRAWING TEST FOR DEMENTIA OF THE ALZHEIMER'S TYPE: A COMPARISON OF TWO SCORING METHODS

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TITLE: THE CLOCK DRAWING TEST FOR DEMENTIA OF THE ALZHEIMER'S TYPE: A COMPARISON OF TWO SCORING METHODS

INTRODUCTION: The Clock Drawing Test (CDT) is an inexpensive, fast and easily administered measure of cognitive function, especially in the elderly. This instrument is a popular clinical tool widely used in screening for cognitive disorders and dementia. The CDT can be applied in different ways and scoring procedures also vary. The aims of this study were to determine the reliability of the CDT and evaluate inter-rater reliability of the CDT scored by using a specific algorithm methods adapted from Sunderland and Shulman.

METHODS: CDT did a total of 141 patients. 52 were diagnosed with Alzheimer's, while another group of 89 patients had mild cognitive impairment. The CDT and Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) were administered to all participants. Two independent examiners scored the CDT to evaluate inter-rater reliability.

RESULTS: The mean MMSE score in patients with Alzheimer's disease (AD) was 18.42, while in patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), the mean value was 25.62 ($p < 0.05$). Two independent researchers evaluated (Shulman D-mean AD 3.81, mean MCI 2.06; Shulman G-mean AD 3.73, mean MCI 1.93, and Sunderland D-mean AD 4.67, mean MCI 7.50; Sunderland G-mean AD 4.46, mean MCI 7.57), the limit value for Shulman is 3, results less than 3 means there is no disorder, and limit value for Sunderland is 6, results greater than 6 indicate that there are no disruptions. There was a high inter-rater reliability between two examiners (Shulman $R = 0.97$, $p < 0.01$; Sunderland $R = 0.98$, $p < 0.01$).

CONCLUSION: It is necessary to administrate CDT in screening for AD because it is easy to perform, and gives a good insight into the cognitive functioning of patients, and objectivity of the examiner, given that different researchers and different readings indicate the degree of impairment in cognitive functioning.

492 THE EFFECTS OF FINASTERIDE ON OXIDATIVE STRESS PARAMETERS AND CELLULAR MARKER EXPRESSION IN RAT BRAIN IN THIOACETAMIDE-INDUCED HEPATIC ENCEPHALOPATHY

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TITLE: THE EFFECTS OF FINASTERIDE ON OXIDATIVE STRESS PARAMETERS AND CELLULAR MARKER EXPRESSION IN RAT BRAIN IN THIOACETAMIDE-INDUCED HEPATIC ENCEPHALOPATHY

INTRODUCTION: Finasteride inhibits neurosteroid synthesis and potentially improves the course of hepatic encephalopathy (HE). The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of finasteride on oxidative stress parameters and cellular marker expression in rat brain in thioacetamide-induced HE.

METHODS: Male Wistar rats were divided into the groups: 1. control; 2. thioacetamide-treated, TAA (900 mg/kg); 3. finasteride-treated, FIN (150 mg/kg); 4. group treated with finasteride and thioacetamide (FIN+TAA). Daily doses of FIN (50 mg/kg) and TAA (300 mg/kg) were administered intraperitoneally during three days and in FIN+TAA group FIN was administered 2h before every dose of TAA. Oxidative stress parameters were determined in the brain 24h after the treatment. The cellular marker expression was determined by Western blot analysis.

RESULTS: Malondialdehyde level was significantly lower in the cortex ($p<0.01$) and higher in the thalamus ($p<0.01$) in FIN+TAA vs. TAA group. In the cortex reduced glutathione (GSH) level was significantly higher in FIN+TAA vs. control. GSH level in caudate nucleus was significantly lower in FIN+TAA vs. control and TAA group ($p<0.01$), while SOD activity was higher in FIN+TAA vs. control ($p<0.05$). FIN pretreatment prevented TAA-induced increase in glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity in the thalamus and decreased GR activity in FIN+TAA vs. control ($p<0.05$). Hippocampal neuronal NeuN expression was significantly lower in TAA group ($p<0.05$), while microglial Iba1 expression was significantly higher in TAA, FIN and FIN+TAA groups vs. control ($p<0.05$). Hippocampal astrocytic GFAP expression was significantly higher in TAA ($p<0.05$) and significantly lower in FIN+TAA ($p<0.05$) vs. control.

CONCLUSION: Finasteride has regionally selective effects on lipid peroxidation in the brain in thioacetamide-induced HE in rats. Although FIN changed the antioxidative enzyme activity, alleviation of oxidative stress does not contribute to the neuroprotective effects of FIN in HE.